

EFFECTS OF FIBER WAVINESS AND BONDING CONDITION ON COMPOSITE PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

Based on a homogenization method, the effects of fiber waviness and fiber-matrix bonding condition on the performance of composite materials are investigated. Due to the nature of the analytical study, only fiber waviness of sinusoidal type is considered. In the analysis of bonding condition effects, both linear shear slip and linear normal separation models are assumed. Numerical results reveal that the composite properties can be greatly affected even when the fiber waviness ratio is very small. It is also concluded that the bonding conditions on the fiber-matrix interfaces have significant effects on the composite performance.

INTRODUCTION

Due to their high stiffness-to-weight and high strength-to-weight ratios, fiber-reinforced polymer matrix composite materials have become very important candidate materials for high-performance structures. Various fiber geometries have been utilized in composite structure constructions, e.g., chopped fibers, swirl mats, woven fabrics, and unidirectional tapes. As compared to straight fibers, curved fibers provide an extra variable - continuous fiber orientation - for composite material and structure designs. Although the use of curved fibers in composite material and structure designs seems promising, the current engineering composites are limited to straight fibers because of lack of efficient tools for design and unavailability of manufacturing facilities. In addition to the positive applications, in fact, curved fibers or wavy layers may take place during composite manufacturing, e.g. thermal processing, filament winding, braiding, and stitching. Both curved fibers and wavy layers can affect the composite material properties and subsequently the structure performance significantly.

In addition to fiber waviness, another important parameter is the bonding condition between fiber and matrix. Perfect bonding is excellent for load transferring between constituents and can result in high Young's modulus for composites. However, high rigidity usually means low toughness which absorbs low energy in damage process. In order to raise the toughness level, the bonding condition should be relatively poor. When a composite structure has misoriented fibers or is exerted by misaligned loading, a high-toughness material is more tolerable and thus desired. It then is obvious that the bonding condition plays a very important role in composite performance.

HOMOGENIZATION METHOD

Based on a rigorous mathematical theory, the homogenization method has become very useful in studying composites with periodic microstructure. The homogenization solution contains two parts, one is the homogenized part which represents the periodically heterogeneous material by "equivalent" homogeneous properties, and the other is the perturbation part which is the disturbance due to local irregularities.

The fundamentals of homogenization method can be found in the articles by Babuska [1] and, Benssusan, Lion, and Papanicoulau [2]. This approach has been applied to many different areas such as the elastic and dielectric response of composites, and the effective properties of soils. Combining with other numerical techniques such as finite element methods, the homogenization method has shown its feasibility in providing reasonable solutions to some engineering problems, e.g. the bounds of material properties and the moduli of braided composites [3], which have neither experimental verification nor rigorous theoretical solution.

1. FUNDAMENTAL EQUATIONS

Consider a composite material consisting of many periodic unites which are made of two constituents. The domain Ω^ϵ of the composite material is shown in Figure 1 while the unit cell Figure 2. The interface between the constituents are assumed to be nonrigid.

Figure 1 - A composite material consisting of periodic units.

Figure 2 - A basic unit cell.

From the linear elasticity theory, the following basic equations: equilibrium equations, constitutive equations, linear strain-displacement relations, and corresponding boundary conditions are employed in this study.

$$\sigma_{ij,j} + f_i = 0 \quad \text{in } \Omega \quad (1)$$

$$\sigma_{ij} = E_{ijkl} e_{kl} \quad \text{in } \Omega \quad (2)$$

$$e_{kl} = \frac{1}{2} (u_{k,j} + u_{j,i}) \quad \text{in } \Omega \quad (3)$$

$$u_i = \tilde{u}_i(\mathbf{x}) \quad \text{on } \Gamma_u \quad (4a)$$

$$\sigma_{ij} n_j = \tilde{T}_i(\mathbf{x}) \quad \text{on } \Gamma_T \quad (4b)$$

In the above equations σ_{ij} , e_{ij} , u_i , and T_i represent stress, strain, displacement, and traction, respectively, while \tilde{u}_i and \tilde{T}_i are specified displacement and traction exerted on the composite boundary. The domain Ω is defined as the domain Ω^c without the interfaces and Γ is the boundary of the composite material.

In formulating the homogenized properties of a composite material with imperfect interfaces, two interfacial conditions are required. In this study, linear interfacial conditions are assumed. When shear slip takes place on an interface between the constituents, the shear traction is assumed to be proportional to the slip in the following manner:

$$T_{S1} = T_{S2} = \frac{1}{\epsilon\mu} [u_{S2} - u_{S1}] \quad (5a)$$

where T_{S1} and T_{S2} are the shear tractions on the interface for individual constituents while u_{S1} and u_{S2} are shearing displacement components. In addition, μ is named shear slip coefficients. If μ approaches infinite, the shear tractions will vanish. Apparently, this represents a condition of no-bonding. On the contrary, when μ becomes zero, the difference of shearing displacements has to be vanished in order to have finite shear tractions. It then is a perfect bonding condition.

Similar linear relation can also be assumed for normal separation and normal tractions on the fiber-matrix interface. i.e.

$$T_{N1} = T_{N2} = \frac{1}{\epsilon k} [u_{N2} - u_{N1}] \quad (5b)$$

It is necessary to point out that

$$u_N = u_i n_i \quad \text{and} \quad (u_S)_i = u_i - u_N n_i \quad (5c)$$

$$T_N = \sigma_{ij} n_i n_j \quad \text{and} \quad (T_S)_i = \sigma_{ij} n_j - \sigma_N n_i \quad (5d)$$

As a consequence, the normal separation coefficient k becomes zero when the interface is perfectly bonded while infinitely large when there is no bonding on the interface. In addition, care should be exercised in numerical process to avoid the physical absurdity of penetration between the constituents sharing the same interface.

2. FORMULATION

A multiple-scale method is used here to study the homogenized problems. Choose \mathbf{x} as the macroscopic variables and \mathbf{y} as the microscopic variables. They are related by $\mathbf{y} = \frac{\mathbf{x}}{\epsilon}$, where ϵ has the order of unit-cell dimensions, which is very small when compared to the dimensions of the composite material.

It is to find the solutions of u_i and σ_{ij} in the following asymptotic expansion forms:

$$u_i(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) = u_i^0(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) + \epsilon u_i^1(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) + \epsilon^2 u_i^2(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y}) + \dots \quad (6a)$$

$$\sigma_{ij}(x, y) = \frac{1}{\epsilon} \sigma_{ij}^0(x, y) + \sigma_{ij}^1(x, y) + \epsilon \sigma_{ij}^2(x, y) + \dots \quad (6b)$$

Since the domain of interest consists of periodically distributed units, both $u_i^n(x, y)$ and $\sigma_{ij}^n(x, y)$ ($n=0,1,2,3,\dots$) should be periodic functions about y . Hence, the mean values of their differentiations with respect to y vanish, i.e.,

$$M[u_{,y_j}^n] = M[\sigma_{,y_j}^n] = 0 \quad n=0, 1, 2, 3,\dots \quad (7a)$$

where

$$M[u] = \frac{1}{|Y|} \int_Y u(x, y) dY \quad (7b)$$

Substituting the asymptotic expansions (6a) and (6b) into Equations (2) and (1), respectively, with the use of linear strain-displacement relations, the following equations can be concluded from comparing the coefficients of the $1/\epsilon^2$ terms on both sides of the equation.

$$\sigma_{ij,y_j}^0 = 0 \quad (8a)$$

$$\sigma_{ij}^0 = E_{ijkl} e_{kl}^y(u_i^0) \quad (8b)$$

where $e_{kl}^y(u_i^0)$ are defined as $e_{kl}^y(u_i^0) = \frac{1}{2}(u_{k,y_l}^0 + u_{l,y_k}^0)$

Similarly, by substituting the asymptotic expansions into Equations (4a) and (4b), u_i^0 and σ_{ij}^0 of the boundary conditions can be expressed as follows

$$u_i^0 = \tilde{u}_i(x) \quad \text{on } \Gamma_u \quad (9a)$$

$$\sigma_{ij,n_j}^0 = 0 \quad \text{on } \Gamma_\sigma \quad (9b)$$

It can be further concluded from Equations (8) and (9) that

$$u_i^0 = u_i^0(x) \quad (10a)$$

$$\sigma_{ij}^0 = 0 \quad (10b)$$

With the same manner as used in deriving Equations (8a) and (8b), the coefficients associated with $1/\epsilon$ term give rise to

$$\sigma_{ij,y_j}^1 = 0 \quad (11a)$$

The above equation can also be expressed in another form

$$\left[E_{ijkl}(y) u_{k,l}^0(x) + E_{ijkl}(y) u_{k,y_l}^1(x, y) \right]_{,y_j} = 0 \quad (11b)$$

By using the technique of separation of variables, the solution of u_i^1 can be found in the following form

$$u_k^1(x, y) = -\chi_g^{kl}(y) u_{k,l}^0(x) \quad (12a)$$

in which χ_g^{kl} should also satisfy $\left(E_{ijgh}(y) \chi_{g,y_h}^{kl}(y) \right)_{,y_j} = E_{ijkl}(y)_{,y_j}$ (12b)

Moreover, from comparing ϵ^0 terms, the following equation can be obtained

$$\sigma_{ij,j}^1 + \sigma_{ij,y_j}^1 + f_i = 0 \quad (13a)$$

in which

$$\sigma_{ij}^1 = \left(E_{ijkl}(\mathbf{y}) - E_{ijgh}(\mathbf{y}) \chi_{g,y_h}^{kl}(\mathbf{y}) \right) u_{k,l}^0(\mathbf{x}) \quad (13b)$$

The associated boundary conditions are as follows.

$$u_i^0 = \tilde{u}_i(\mathbf{x}) \quad \text{on } \Gamma_u \quad (13c)$$

$$\sigma_{ij}^1 n_j = \tilde{\sigma}_i(\mathbf{x}) \quad \text{on } \Gamma_T$$

In addition, giving the following definitions,

$$\tau_{ij} = M[\sigma_{ij}^1(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{y})] \quad (14a)$$

$$E_{ijkl}^H = M[E_{ijkl} - E_{ijgh} \chi_{g,y_h}^{kl}] \quad (14b)$$

the formulae for solving homogenized problems can be rewritten as follows:

$$\tau_{ij,j} + f_i = 0 \quad \text{in } \Omega \quad (15a)$$

$$\tau_{ij} = E_{ijkl}^H e_{kl}(u_i^0) \quad \text{in } \Omega \quad (15b)$$

in conjunction with the boundary conditions

$$u_i^0 = \tilde{u}_i(\mathbf{x}) \quad \text{on } \Gamma_u \quad (15c)$$

$$\tau_{ij} n_j = \tilde{\sigma}_i(\mathbf{x}) \quad \text{on } \Gamma_\sigma \quad (15d)$$

It should be noted that Equations (15) are the statement of equilibrium in a macroscopic sense, and the homogenized material properties are defined by Equations (14b), i.e.,

$$E_{ijkl}^H = M[E_{ijkl} - E_{ijgh} \chi_{g,y_h}^{kl}] = \frac{1}{|Y|} \int_Y (E_{ijkl} - E_{ijgh} \chi_{g,y_h}^{kl}) dY \quad (16)$$

where $\chi_g^{kl}(\mathbf{y})$ satisfy both periodic conditions and composite interfacial conditions, i.e.

$$\left(E_{ijkl} - E_{ijgh} \chi_{g,y_h}^{kl} \right)_{S1} = \frac{1}{\mu} \left[\left(\chi_g^{kl} \right)_{S1} - \left(\chi_g^{kl} \right)_{S2} \right] \quad (17a)$$

$$\left(E_{ijkl} - E_{ijgh} \chi_{g,y_h}^{kl} \right)_{S2} = \frac{1}{\mu} \left[\left(\chi_g^{kl} \right)_{S1} - \left(\chi_g^{kl} \right)_{S2} \right] \quad (17b)$$

$$\left(E_{ijkl} - E_{ijgh} \chi_{g,y_h}^{kl} \right)_{N1} = \frac{1}{k} \left[\left(\chi_g^{kl} \right)_{N1} - \left(\chi_g^{kl} \right)_{N2} \right] \quad (17c)$$

$$\left(E_{ijkl} - E_{ijgh} \chi_{g,y_h}^{kl} \right)_{N2} = \frac{1}{k} \left[\left(\chi_g^{kl} \right)_{N1} - \left(\chi_g^{kl} \right)_{N2} \right] \quad (17d)$$

As a summary, two decoupled problems are being solved by homogenization method. One is the microscopic solution for $\chi_g^{kl}(\mathbf{y})$ from Equation (12b) and periodic conditions and interfacial Equations, (17). Then, the effective moduli can be calculated from equation (16). The other is the macroscopic solution for $u_i^0(\mathbf{x})$ which are set up by Equations (15). Once these two solutions are found, the displacement field u_i up to the first order term of ϵ (Equation (6a)) and the stress field (Equation (13b)) can be determined.

3. APPLICATIONS

3.1 Composites with Straight Fibers

The unit cell of the structure is shown in Figure 3. This is a one-dimensional case and is possible to have an analytical solution. With the use of the formulae presented in the previous sections, the distribution function of a composite material with imperfect bonding can be obtained.

Figure 3 - A periodic unit combining fiber and matrix.

Consider that a composite material is made of two constituents as shown above. One is denoted as E_{ijkl}^f and the other E_{ijkl}^m . Assume both the constituents are orthotropic and the composite is also an orthotropic material. Then $\chi_g^{kl}(y)$ can be written as

$$\chi_g^{kl}(y) = A_g^{kl} y_2 + B_g^{kl}$$

where

$$A_1^{kl} = \frac{b(E_{12kl}^f - E_{12kl}^m) + \mu E_{12kl}^f E_{1212}^m}{\mu E_{1212}^f E_{1212}^m + (a E_{1212}^m + b E_{1212}^f)}, \quad A_2^{kl} = \frac{b(E_{22kl}^f - E_{22kl}^m) + k E_{22kl}^f E_{2222}^m}{k E_{2222}^f E_{2222}^m + (a E_{2222}^m + b E_{2222}^f)}$$

in fiber domain, and

$$A_1^{kl} = \frac{-a(E_{12kl}^f - E_{12kl}^m) + \mu E_{12kl}^m E_{1212}^f}{\mu E_{1212}^f E_{1212}^m + (a E_{1212}^m + b E_{1212}^f)}, \quad A_2^{kl} = \frac{-a(E_{22kl}^f - E_{22kl}^m) + k E_{22kl}^m E_{2222}^f}{k E_{1212}^f E_{1212}^m + (a E_{1212}^m + b E_{1212}^f)}$$

in matrix domain. In addition, it should be noted that B_g^{kl} in fiber is equal to $B_g^{kl} + (a + b) A_g^{kl}$ in matrix.

3.2 Composites with Sinusoidally Curved Fiber

Figure 4 - A unit cell with sinusoidal curvature

Again, consider a composite material consisting of two orthotropic constituents. An attempt is made to find an analytical solution for effective moduli. In the case of small amplitude of curvature, $\chi_g^{kl}(y)$ has the following form

$$\chi_g^{kl}(\mathbf{y}) = A_g^{kl}(y_2 - \alpha \sin \beta y_1) + B_g^{kl} + \alpha G_g(y_2 - \alpha \sin \beta y_1) \cos \beta y_2 + \alpha H_g(y_2 - \alpha \sin \beta y_1) \sin \beta y_1$$

where α is a small quantity, i.e. $\alpha \ll 1$. After some variable transformation, it is found that G_g and H_g satisfy linear ordinary differential equations. It then is possible to obtain the analytical solution with the periodic conditions and interfacial bonding conditions.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

Numerical results for fiber waviness effects are shown in Figure 5. The Young's modulus in the axial direction seems to be significantly affected even the waviness ratio (defined as the ratio of wavy amplitude to unit length) is very small. However, the effects of the waviness on the Young's modulus in the transverse direction and the shear modulus are almost unnoticeable.

Numerical results for the effects of bonding conditions on the composite properties are depicted in Figure 6. Opposite to the waviness effects, the Young's modulus in the transverse direction and the shear modulus are very sensitive to the bonding condition while the Young's modulus in the axial direction is not. The same conclusions can also be drawn from the analysis of the two Poisson's ratios.

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Figure 5 - Effects of interfacial imperfection on moduli of composites with straight fibers.

Figure 6 - Effects of fiber waviness on Young's moduli and shear modulus.